

DELIVERABLE 4.1

ADVOCACY PLAN

FOR INTERACTION WITH

HIGHER LEVEL AUTHORITIES

AUTHORS

Anna Bruen, ICLEI European Secretariat
Dorina Meyer, ICLEI European Secretariat
May 2023

PROJECT ACRONYM:	FoodCLIC
PROJECT NUMBER:	101060717
WORK PACKAGE NUMBER AND TITLE:	WP4 – Mutual learning, networking, evidence-based guidelines and tools
LEAD BENEFICIARY:	ICLEI ES
WORK PACKAGE LEADER:	SURREY
RELEVANT TASK:	T4.2 – Exchange with relevant public authorities at regional, provincial, national and European level
DISSEMINATION LEVEL:	Public
DUE DATE (MONTH):	M9, May 2023
VERSION:	Revised version review period 1 June 17, 2024

Funded by
the European Union

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. Introduction.....	5
1.1 FoodCLIC Advocacy Roles and Responsibilities	5
1.2 Objectives and desired impacts	6
2. The CLIC Framework for integrated FOOD policy	7
3. The policy context	8
4. Advocacy topics and talking points	11
4.1 Climate & Nature.....	11
Pitches and talking points	11
4.2 Food Security and Sovereignty	12
Pitches and Talking Points	13
4.3 Health	13
Pitches and Talking points.....	14
4.4 Urban/Rural	15
Pitches and Talking Points	16
5. Opportunities and timeline	17
5.1 Activities and Events	17
5.1.1 FoodCLIC Planned Events	17
5.1.2 FoodCLIC Advocacy Opportunities and related KPIs	19

Annex

HISTORY OF CHANGE

June 17, 2024

Number	Page	Change
1	19	Chapter 5.1.1 FoodCLIC Planned Events added estimated timeline for LL policy dialogues (Table 2).
2	23	Chapter 5.1.2 FoodCLIC Advocacy Opportunities And Related KPIs updated advocacy priorities for the LLs (Table 2: Advocacy Priorities of City-regions).

1. INTRODUCTION

This advocacy plan for interaction with higher level authorities outlines overall objectives and specific opportunities to position, report on and share FoodCLIC's relevance for policy making. The advocacy activities begin in May 2023 and will continue throughout the duration of the project. The plan outlines pitches, talking points and opportunities for partners to act as ambassadors and influence key policy and decision makers to facilitate the transformation of food systems across Europe to include healthy, sustainable, safe, and affordable food environments.

Effective and targeted outreach and advocacy activities are crucial to mainstream food into appropriate policy areas and to scale out FoodCLIC beyond the scope of the project timeline. This advocacy plan focuses on European policy, with a particular focus on the Member States and regions of the eight partner city-regions (Aarhus, Denmark; Metropolitan area of Barcelona, Spain; Berlin, Germany; Metropolitan Area Brasov, Romania; Budapest, Hungary; Lisbon Metropolitan Area, Portugal; Metropolitan Region of Amsterdam, Netherlands; and Plain of Lucca, Italy) and European broadening regions (to be determined). By strategically connecting to EU and UN-level processes and frameworks to advocate with and for Member State-level and regional public authorities, we seek to raise awareness, create acknowledgement of and buy-in for the need to create food environments that enable the transformation of food systems across Europe.

This strategy will be updated on an annual basis to account for new opportunities that may be relevant to maximise the outreach and impact of FoodCLIC.

1.1 FOODCLIC ADVOCACY ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES

The advocacy activities are aligned with the project's Communication and Dissemination plan (D5.2), coordinated by ICLEI ES as WP5 leader. The plan will be implemented in close collaboration with SURREY as lead of WP4. All WP4 and WP5 partners, especially Think Tank members and Living Lab partners, will act as ambassadors and be mobilised using synergies with other work in FoodCLIC and available resources. Relevant data and information coming out of the FoodCLIC project will be sought from project partners in order to refine and further strengthen the evidence base of the advocacy messages. Living Lab partners' work will feature in advocacy and outreach activities and the Living Lab partners will take the lead to organise two advocacy events in their region (with

support from WP4 and WP5). More generally, key project results that are potentially relevant for policy making will feed into the planning of advocacy activities.

1.2 OBJECTIVES AND DESIRED IMPACTS

FoodCLIC's primary advocacy objectives are to:

- Secure support for government and non-government stakeholders to strengthen their collaboration and deepen their understanding of city-region food systems
- Build a foundation for establishing food-sensitive policy and planning frameworks influenced by systemic (rather than siloed) thinking and approaches
- Mainstream food in planning frameworks related to land-use, circularity, climate and resilience action, and health
- Accelerate the adoption of lessons learned from the application of the CLIC framework
- Strengthen the multi-level governance of food systems in order to connect city-region food systems in policy and practice

The desired impacts of advocacy activities include:

- Increased awareness of food-related policy concerns across sectors (e.g., environment, health, welfare)
- Increased awareness of the importance of multi-stakeholder engagement in designing and implementing food policies
- Increased capacity of policy makers to positively impact food environments and accelerate the development of integrated food policies based on the CLIC framework
- Mainstreaming the CLIC into policy and planning frameworks in order to develop policy coherence

2. THE CLIC FRAMEWORK FOR INTEGRATED FOOD POLICY

The CLIC framework¹ counteracts the pervasive siloed mentality that permeates food policy and governance – i.e., the tendency to operate within, rather than across, the sectoral boundaries that traditionally separate the food system from other complex systems (e.g., environment, health, economic, welfare). The CLIC incorporates the place-based and multi-dimensional nature of food system transformation by working under the assumption that food systems are currently under high pressure from climate change, environmental pollution, obesity and non-communicable diseases and an increasing demand for food. FoodCLIC recognises the urgent need for these food, and related, systems to transform. The CLIC Framework outlines a direction for food sustainability agendas that emphasises four key dimensions of integration – social, environmental, spatial, and sectoral – in order to realise holistic food system transformation. The CLIC is built on four pillars, which can be seen as FoodCLIC’s (interrelated) goals for food system transformation:

- **Co-benefits.** Fostering ‘co-benefits’ recognizes that sustainability strategies with specific economic, social or environmental goals may impact other parts of a system in a positive or negative way, creating synergies or trade-offs (e.g. social/health, economic, environmental).
- **Linkages.** Establishing “linkages” refers to positive flows, connections and interactions, as opposed to fixed boundaries, and adds a territorial dimension to co-benefits, focusing attention on (re)establishing or strengthening positive spatial, socio-cultural, economic and environmental relations between communities and localities and, more broadly, between “the urban” and “the rural” and the land and the water. The concept of linkages brings into focus the networked interdependencies between the city and the countryside.
- **Inclusion.** The “inclusion” of all food system stakeholders and groups of actors (from science, policy, practice, including food deprived and vulnerable groups) emphasizes not just the empowerment of different communities through enhanced participation, local leadership, ownership, and control of initiatives but also, importantly, the role of experiential and scientific knowledge mutually informing each other.
- **Connectivity.** Building and strengthening “connectivity” refers to the physical and virtual relationships (or lack thereof) between what and how we eat and wider sets of public goods (such as health, wellbeing, the environment, and the welfare system) that, like food, are governed at multiple scales. For example, food system transformation connects with context-dependent concerns around climate change, resource scarcity, biodiversity conservation, sustainable transport, affordable housing, and employment.

¹ The CLIC framework has been derived from Sonnino, R. & Milbourne, P. (2022) Food system transformation: a progressive place-based approach, *Local Environment*, 27:7, 915-926, DOI: [10.1080/13549839.2022.2084723](https://doi.org/10.1080/13549839.2022.2084723)

3. THE POLICY CONTEXT

The first international agreement on sustainable urban food systems was launched by the City of Milan in 2015 with the support of over 100 other cities signing the [Milan Urban Food Policy Pact \(MUFPP\)](#). MUFPP is a commitment "to develop sustainable food systems that are inclusive, resilient, safe and diverse, that provide healthy and affordable food to all people in a human rights-based framework, that minimize waste and conserve biodiversity while adapting to and mitigating impacts of climate change".² The commitment consists of 37 actions and a monitoring framework for mayors and policy makers to work together to address food related challenges at the urban level. To date, over 200 cities have signed the Pact and representatives have been activating the network to advocate for active roles for cities in international and global initiatives such as the UN Sustainable Development goals, and the anticipated food-related activities and policies at the EU level, such as those in the European Green Deal, Farm to Fork Strategy, and Sustainable Food Systems Law.

As part of the [European Green Deal](#), approved in 2020, the European Commission (EC) committed to be the world's first 'climate-neutral bloc' by 2050. The European Green Deal intends to transform the EU 'into a modern, resource-efficient and competitive economy' ensuring no net emissions of greenhouse gases by 2050, economic growth decoupled from resource use, and no person and no place left behind in the transition to a greener economy. Its goals cover many different sectors including construction, biodiversity, energy, transport, and food, and the set of policy initiatives that make up the European Green Deal are targeted to improve the well-being and health of citizens. At the heart of the Deal is the [Farm to Fork \(F2F\) Strategy](#).

The Farm to Fork Strategy aims to create food environments that make it possible and easier for people to choose healthy and sustainable diets and sets goals to ensure sustainable food production; ensure food security; stimulate sustainable food processing, wholesale, retail, hospitality, and food services practices; promote sustainable food consumption and facilitate the shift to healthy, sustainable diets; reducing food loss and waste; and combat food fraud along the food supply chain³. To meet these goals F2F sets concrete targets and announced that the Commission will put forth a proposal for a new Legislative Framework for [Sustainable Food Systems Law](#) (SFS law) by the end of 2023.

This SFS law is one of the flagship initiatives of the F2F and the first of its kind. It is expected to accelerate the transition to a sustainable food system, promote policy coherence and integration at

²

³ https://food.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2020-05/f2f_action-plan_2020_strategy-info_en.pdf

the EU and national levels, mainstream sustainability in food-related policies, put forth a food labelling framework, and strengthen the resilience of food systems⁴. It will include common definitions and general principles and requirements for a sustainable food system where food is viewed more as a common good than a commodity⁵. Results of the JRC's public participation process to explore building blocks for the legislative framework indicate strong recognition and support of engaging with power dynamics in the food system, making healthy and sustainable food choices easier for consumers, and the need for multi-scale and integrated governance⁶.

Following the launch of the SFS law, the European Commission together with Member States is establishing the 'Partnership for Sustainable Food Systems (SFS) for people, planet, and climate'. SFS is expected to launch at the beginning of 2024. It aims to transform national, EU and global food systems, making them safe, sustainable, healthy, resilient and trusted – for everyone and within planetary boundaries and to help bridge science-policy topics and education. The Partnership's mission is to mobilise research and innovation (R&I) to accelerate the transition towards sustainable food systems with a wide range of actors taking action⁷. The partnership will facilitate joint funding of R&I for food systems transformation, launch a food systems observatory, establish a food systems knowledge hub, and provide knowledge sharing and scaling and competence building/education, including scientific advice for policy making. Preparatory actions to establish the future Partnership are underway and guided by DG RTD of the European Commission and the SCAR Strategic Working Group Food Systems by means of the [FoodPathS project](#).

Providing a basis for much of this work is DG Research and Innovation's [Food2030](#) policy framework, which aims to accelerate a transition to sustainable and resilient food systems within safe planetary boundaries⁸. Launched in 2015 after the Milan World Expo, it aligns with and supports the goal of the European Green Deal, F2F and the bioeconomy strategy. The main goals of Food2030 are to address interconnected challenges across the food system and to realise a range of co-benefits by focusing on 1) nutrition for sustainable and healthy diets, 2) food systems supporting a healthy diet, 3) circularity and resource efficiency, 4) innovation and the empowerment of communities. The pathways of action to achieve these goals align with the Partnership for Sustainable Food Systems, as well as the Mission Area: Soil Health and Food. The [EU Mission: A Soil Deal for Europe](#) recognises that life on earth depends on healthy soils and will establish 100 living labs and lighthouses to lead the transition towards healthy soils by 2030. Soil is the foundation of our food systems and provides clean water and habitats for biodiversity while contributing to

⁴ https://food.ec.europa.eu/horizontal-topics/farm-fork-strategy/legislative-framework_en

⁵ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Group of Chief Scientific Advisors, *Towards a sustainable food system : moving from food as a commodity to food as more of a common good : independent expert report*, Publications Office, 2020, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/282386>

⁶ Bock, A., Bontoux, L. and Rudkin, J., *Concepts for a sustainable EU food system*, EUR 30894 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2022, ISBN 978-92-76-43727-7, doi:10.2760/381319, JRC126575.

⁷ <https://www.foodpaths.eu/sfs-partnership/>

⁸ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/research-area/environment/bioeconomy/food-systems/food-2030_en

climate resilience. Additionally, it supports our cultural heritage and landscapes and is the basis for much economic activity.

The CLIC provides a framework to ground global abstract conversations and policy ambitions with local/regional realities for real food system transformation at the level where people and the planet are directly impacted – place-based food environments. Place-based food environments implicate local, regional, and global connectivities and the visible/mainstream activities as well as hidden/marginal activities, which in turn extend to national and global systems. The CLIC provides a framework to understand, evaluate, and spur action on complex and connected facets of the food system⁹. It can support the just transition to sustainable and resilient food systems by prompting, reminding, and checking that policy and action provide co-benefits, linkages, inclusiveness, and connectivity.

⁹ Sonnino, R. & Milbourne, P. (2022) Food system transformation: a progressive place-based approach, *Local Environment*, 27:7, 915-926, DOI: 10.1080/13549839.2022.2084723

4. ADVOCACY TOPICS AND TALKING POINTS

The following agenda topics and associated groups, platforms and processes provide the most promising opportunities for outreach and advocacy:

4.1 CLIMATE & NATURE

Considering consumption patterns, land-use change, agricultural production, packaging, and waste management, food systems produce more than one third (approx. 34%) of global greenhouse gas emissions¹⁰. Additionally, human destruction of nature has caused a 69% reduction in species population since 1970 and food systems are a primary driver of biodiversity loss through unsustainable food production methods, which contribute to habitat loss. There are many initiatives at the EU level to reverse these trends, including:

- EU Missions: [Adaptation to Climate Change](#), [A Soil Deal for Europe](#), [Climate Neutral and Smart Cities](#)
- Proposed [Nature Restoration Law](#)
- [Green City Accord](#)
- [Biodiversity Strategy 2030](#)
- [Edinburgh Declaration](#)
- [Berlin Urban Nature Pact](#)
- [Glasgow Food and Climate Declaration](#)

Aligning with projects, events, and activities targeting climate adaptation, resilience, enhancing biodiversity, and protecting nature provides FoodCLIC the opportunity to facilitate policy integration in order to realise co-benefits from taking advantage of synergistic priorities across sectors.

PITCHES AND TALKING POINTS

- **Considering CLIC in policy development can prompt solutions that will reduce biodiversity and soil loss, food waste and GHG emissions.**

¹⁰ <https://www.nature.com/articles/s43016-021-00225-9>

- Food loss and waste contributes approximately 10% of GHG emissions. Addressing them has the potential to reduce the climate impact of food production and consumption while saving resources for primary producers and companies and providing more food for people to eat¹¹, indicating the importance of CLIC's dimension of looking for “co-benefits.’
- In order to reduce cities’ or countries’ scope 1, 2, and 3 emissions from food systems, (direct, indirect from electricity, and all other indirect), working across policy sectors (the CLIC’s dimension of “connectivities”) is crucial.
- The production and consumption of meat is a major polluting agricultural factor. A positive impact on GHG emissions can be realised by reducing conventional meat production and consumption and promoting plant based diets.
- Connecting environmental and climate strategies with food policy creates linkages between what and how food is produced, available, and accessible, how food is packaged and distributed, and how food waste is managed. This provides additional opportunities to address the needs of food deprived people and realise co-benefits for people and the planet.
- Growing, sourcing, and preparing the ingredients for meals in canteens in a sustainable way is important for municipalities and countries to achieve the targets of the UN Sustainable Development Goals and the Paris Agreement on climate change. The CLIC offers a systemic approach to tasks related to this, such as public food procurement.

4.2 FOOD SECURITY AND SOVEREIGNTY

According to FAO, conflict, climate, and economic slowdowns and downturns are the main causes of food insecurity. A person is food insecure when they lack regular access to enough safe and nutritious food for normal growth and development and an active and healthy life. This may be due to unavailability of food and/or lack of resources to obtain food. Food insecurity can be experienced at different levels of severity¹². Severe food insecurity occurs when someone goes a day or more without food and experiences hunger, and an estimated 8% of the world’s population will experience hunger in 2030¹³. More moderate (yet also worrisome) food insecurity is when people have to sacrifice other basic needs to be able to eat. Food insecurity is correlated with mental, emotional, and physical health problems, as well as with chronic disease. Proactive policies, trade and market interventions, and subsidies to producers and consumers can help improve the availability and affordability of healthy diets.

¹¹ https://food.ec.europa.eu/horizontal-topics/farm-fork-strategy/food-loss-and-waste-prevention_en

¹² <https://www.fao.org/hunger/en/>

¹³ FAO, IFAD, UNICEF, WFP and WHO. 2022. *The State of Food Security and Nutrition in the World 2022. Repurposing food and agricultural policies to make healthy diets more affordable*. Rome, FAO. <https://doi.org/10.4060/cc0639en>

Food sovereignty is defined by the global peasant movement La Via Campesina as “the right of peoples to healthy and culturally appropriate food produced through ecologically sound and sustainable methods, and their right to define their own food and agriculture systems.”¹⁴ At its core, food sovereignty is focused on re-balancing power in the food system and distributing power to the people who produce, distribute and consume food and away from corporations and institutions.

PITCHES AND TALKING POINTS

- FoodCLIC recognizes that we need policy solutions and interventions at multiple scales to address food security and sovereignty issues. Policies need to be place-based, meaningfully inclusive of food deprived and vulnerable groups, and connect to other policy sectors such as climate, health, security, and trade.
- We need integrated policies that proactively support affordable access to nutritious and culturally appropriate food. This could be done by repurposing food and agriculture policy and subsidies for the support of affordable access to nutritious food.
- Unsustainable food systems create fragile supply chains that are particularly susceptible to sudden shocks, whereas a sustainable supply chain can make a significant impact in promoting human rights, fair labour practices, and anti-corruption policies. Urban agriculture is one tool to decrease food insecurity in local areas.
- Resilient food systems depend on diversity. Yet, small-scale farmers, fishers, and workers involved in harvesting and processing are struggling to earn a living wage. The CLIC framework can help ensure that policies are inclusive and beneficial to a wide group of stakeholders.
- Reducing food loss and waste as early as possible in the supply chain leads to greater food security.

4.3 HEALTH

FoodCLIC recognises the linkages between healthy people, healthy climate, and healthy landscapes. Local, national, international, and global organisations such as the World Health Organisation (WHO) and Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations (FAO), World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH), and the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) recognise the need for

¹⁴ <https://viacampesina.org/en/food-sovereignty-a-manifesto-for-the-future-of-our-planet-la-via-campesina/>

interdisciplinary and systemic approaches to the prevention, education, investment, and policy development related to health. 'One health' lies at the intersection of human health, animal health, and environmental health. WHO defines 'one health' as an integrated, unifying approach to balance and optimise the health of people, animals, and the environment.' The 'one health' approach mobilises stakeholders and sectors throughout the food system – public health, animal health, environmental health – and encourages multi-level governance in order to develop new and better ideas to address the root causes of unsustainable food systems and create long-term solutions.

Healthy food relies on healthy environments. FoodCLIC advocates for reducing consumption of highly processed and packaged foods (high in trans fats, sugar, salt and chemical additives) delivered by unsustainable food systems, which are characterised by the use of carbon-intensive production methods, based on the heavy use of artificial fertilisers and pesticides, conducive to soil and resource depletion as well as a disregard of animal welfare issues.

PITCHES AND TALKING POINTS

- We need the CLIC's focus on inclusion and connectivity for food and health policies that enable easy and affordable access to healthy and sustainable food. More than 50% of adults and almost 1 in 3 children are overweight or living with obesity, this leads to other diet-related health problems (e.g. diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, and certain cancers).
- We need a food systems approach to health and nutrition education to promote healthy nutritional habits. This has implications for the whole food system. Applying the CLIC framework can help identify co-benefits, important linkages, increase inclusivity, and make connections to ensure a healthy and sustainable transformation to benefit people and the planet.
- We need the CLIC's 'inclusion' focus to create policies that support procurement of nutritious and sustainable food. Vulnerable people, such as children who receive the majority of their nutrition via school meals, the elderly or those in long-term care facilities are at risk of hunger and malnutrition.
- We need food environments with easy access to healthy food for all age groups and socio-economic classes. We need dietary guidelines, economic, and agricultural policies that incentivise healthy and 'climate-friendly' food from production to processing to consumption to compost. The CLIC's focus on co-benefits, linkages, inclusion, and connectivity supports this.
- The goal of food policies should be to provide for safe, wholesome, nutritious, culturally appropriate food (supply) that is financially and physically accessible for everyone, and available in adequate amounts to promote health, prevent dietary deficiency, and reduce other diet-related diseases. The CLIC's focus on co-benefits, linkages, inclusion, and connectivity helps make this happen.

- We need health education that teaches children about the connections between food production, processing, distribution, and consumption – from a global, local, regional and seasonal perspective and encourages understanding of how food choices impact the environment, human health, and the food system as a whole. The CLIC’s focus on co-benefits and connectivities underscores this importance.
- We need to promote culturally appropriate and diversified diets supported by health education that emphasize nutrition and the significance of balanced diets, portion control, mindful eating and the importance of consuming whole foods like fruits, beans, whole grains and lean proteins. The CLIC’s focus on co-benefits and connectivities underscores this importance.

4.4 URBAN/RURAL

More than 50% of the world population lives in urban areas, and this percentage is expected to increase to close to 70% by 2050, including relocations of displaced peoples (UN Desa 2022). This growth creates stress on all systems (housing, natural resources, basic services, jobs etc), especially land-use. Urban areas are responsible for more than 75% of natural resource consumption, 60% of GHG emissions, and 50% of the world’s waste. However, they also produce more than 80% of global GDP and have a large potential to contribute to sustainable, nature-positive growth, if managed responsibly¹⁵.

Managing socially desirable levels of population density and land-use while ensuring access to nature and the health of people and the planet, requires being mindful of and re-thinking urbanisation and sprawl¹⁶. Encouraging rural-urban interaction and establishing integrated urban/rural governance, policies, and processes that consider, among others, territorial relationships, transportation, ecosystem services and connectivity, can help realise co-benefits instead of creating negative externalities, as when policies are designed to serve the interests of only one type of place¹⁷.

Of particular relevance to FoodCLIC are the co-benefits for people and the planet when sustainable food system priorities are integrated into urban, land-use and transportation planning, and the potential to shorten supply chains, source healthy food and take care of vulnerable groups of people. Recognising, understanding, and working with the linkages between urban and rural areas can help establish communities of people and resilient habitats for plants and animals.

¹⁵ <https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/urbandevelopment/overview>

¹⁶ <https://www.oecd.org/environment/tools-evaluation/Policy-Highlights-Rethinking-Urban-Sprawl.pdf>

¹⁷ <https://rural-urban.eu/publications/manifesto-future-policy-making-linkages-and-dependencies-between-urban-and-rural>

PITCHES AND TALKING POINTS

- The CLIC's focus on 'linkages' recognises that the rural and urban are not separate, but interdependent. By treating them separately in policy development, the reasons urban areas need rural spaces get overlooked and rural areas are left-behind. Healthy, sustainable, and fair food systems depend on what is happening in urban, peri-urban, and rural landscapes.
- We need to respond to how the local place is lived-in, not to borders that only work on paper. We need to provide opportunities for governance and decision making that is informed from bottom-up knowledge and needs, and fosters cooperation between stakeholders active in rural and urban areas. The CLIC's emphasis on co-benefits, linkages, inclusion, and connectivity supports this.
- We need development policies that are human and nature-centred and enable regions to focus on their competitive strengths to realise co-benefits for people and the planet. We need "growth" that prioritises what a place-based economy can do best – not what it should do or used to do. The CLIC's dimensions of on co-benefits, linkages, inclusion, and connectivity supports this.
- The future of food is at risk – the average age of farmers in the EU is between 50 and 60¹⁸ and farm income has been flatlining with an average hourly wage of €8.70 ¹⁹compared to €23.10 for non-agricultural jobs²⁰. We need to create healthy and attractive economic conditions to encourage the next generation of farmers and farm workers for the benefit of people and nature. The emphasis of CLIC on linkages and co-benefits highlights this importance.

¹⁸<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877042816306140/pdf?md5=51513f277f2027d4601e2ff38913f28a&pid=1-s2.0-S1877042816306140-main.pdf>

¹⁹ https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2021-11/eu-farm-econ-overview-2018_en_0.pdf

²⁰ <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-eurostat-news/-/EDN-20180322-1>

Month	Calendar month	What?	Level	Advocacy
6	Feb-23	WP2 - Deliverable 2.1 - Report on facilitators of, and barriers to development and implementation of evidence-based and integrated food policies and plans		
7	Mar-23			
8	Apr-23	City Food Policy Symposium, 27 Apr. 2023, London, UK 4th Global Conference of the Sustainable Food Systems Programme, 24-27 Apr. 2023, Ha Noi, Vietnam (in person with online)	Global	
9	May-23	Forum Compraverde Buygreen, Italy, 17-18 May 2023 WP4 - Milestone 13 - 1st FPN platform development workshop held	International	
10	Jun-23	EU Green Week 2023, 3-11 June 2023	International	
		Sustainable Foods Summit, 15-16 June 2023, Amsterdam, Netherlands	International	
		ICLEI Member Webinar on Food, 7 June 2023	International	
		Daring Cities 2023 Dialogues, 12-13 June 2023, Bonn Germany, A just and equitable climate emergency response		
		Brussels Urban Summit 2023, Urban answers to global challenges, 12-15 June 2023, metropolis	Global	
11	Jul-23	2023 UN Food Systems Stocktaking Moment, 24-26 July 2023, Rome, Italy, hosted by Italy + FAO, IFAD, WFP, UN Food Systems Summit	Global	
		Women Deliver 2023 Conference (WD2023), Kigali, Rwanda, 17-20 July 2023	Global	
12	Aug-23	WP2 - Deliverable 2.2 - Report on food-related policies and planning frameworks and initiatives in the eight city-regions and at national level		
13	Sep-23	WP1 - Milestone 11 - 3rd training of Living Lab teams on visioning and system analysis		
		Africa's Food Systems Forum (Pre-summit, 4 Sept. 2023); Summit 5-8 Sept. 2023	Global	
14	Oct-23	WP3 - Milestone 14 - City-region multi-stakeholder workshop on system analysis and visioning		
		EURESFO (European Urban Resilience Forum), Cascais (PT), 18-20 Oct. 2023;	International	
		21st #EURegionsWeek (European Week of Regions and Cities), 9-12 Oct. 2023	International	
		World Food Forum (WFF), 16-20 Oct. 2023, UN FAO headquarters, Rome, Italy	International	

Figure 1: Current Advocacy Planning as of May 2023

At the FoodCLIC project level, a series of side events (during European FOOD2030 High Level Events, European R&I Days, European Urban Resilience Forum, European Conference on Sustainable Cities and Towns, EU Week of Regions and Cities, EU Green Week, The Future of Food Conference, and the Sustainable Food Summit MUFPP Annual Gatherings, World Food Days, etc.) will target public authorities at higher levels of governance. During these events, the work of the city-regions will be presented to inspire other city-regions and discuss the type of support that national governments could provide to facilitate the transformation of urban food systems across Europe. [Advocacy opportunities](#), see image 1, current advocacy plan as of May 2023, a (internal) working document will be updated as new information becomes available. It outlines roles and responsibilities and presentation topics (e.g., project outcomes and advocacy topics). Table 1, Advocacy Priorities of City-regions indicates known policy priorities for each of the eight city-regions, it will be updated as more information becomes available.

5.1.1 FOODCLIC PLANNED EVENTS

In addition to being present at global, international, and sectoral events, FoodCLIC will organise one mid-term international conference (M26) and one final international conference (M49/53) that will also provide advocacy opportunities. In addition, each city-region will organise two meetings with their regional/ provincial and national governments to advocate for the role played by cities and city-regions in food system transformation and inspire higher level policy change. Due to the city-level advocacy work needed, some living labs engaged/will engage more intensively with their city-level representatives rather than regional or national.

Table 1. Estimated timeline for LL policy dialogues

CITY-REGION	POLICY DIALOGUE 1	POLICY DIALOGUE 2	POLICY DIALOGUE 3 (OPTIONAL)
Aarhus	<p>November 30th, 2023</p> <p>Aarhus Annual Climate Conference - "The sustainable food system of the future: From global perspective to local actions "workshop.</p> <p><i>Purpose:</i> discuss challenges and opportunities of implementing a sustainable food system in Aarhus in relation to climate.</p> <p><i>Attendees:</i> municipal, regional, and national representation.</p>	<p>Before the end of the FoodCLIC project</p>	<p>Not applicable</p>
Amsterdam	<p>September 7th, 2023</p> <p><i>Attendees:</i> municipal, provincial, and ministerial government representation.</p> <p><i>Purpose:</i> advocate for the importance of food security and sovereignty in neighborhoods in Amsterdam.</p>	<p>Before the end of the project</p>	<p>Not applicable</p>
Barcelona	<p>2025/2026 potentially in collaboration with CleverFoods project.</p>	<p>Before the end of the project</p>	<p>Not applicable</p>
Berlin	<p>July 5th, 2023</p> <p><i>Purpose:</i> civil society organisations to represent their work priorities and get to know the new government representatives & government to present their priorities.</p> <p><i>Attendees:</i> Request for stakeholder meeting with the newly elected senator for Justice and Consumer Protection, Dr. Felor Badenber. Instead of the Senator, the state secretary attended the meeting, Ms. Uleer.</p> <p><i>Chaired by:</i> Lisa Haarhoff, Berlin Food Policy Council.</p> <p>Also attended by civil society organisations: Weltacker, Kate, LMP-Netzwerk, Restlos Glücklich,</p>	<p>November 29th, 2023</p> <p><i>Purpose:</i> Parliamentary hearing on the implementation of the Berlin food strategy.</p> <p><i>Chair:</i> Sven Rissmann (CDU).</p> <p><i>Attendees:</i> Members of the Committee for Constitutional and Legal Affairs, Rules of Procedure, consumer protection.</p>	<p>In collaboration with the CleverFoods project AND/OR one policy workshop in the final year of the FoodCLIC project.</p>

	Verbraucherzentrale Berlin, Sarah Wiener Stiftung, Kleingartenkolonie.		
Brasov	Under discussion, potentially in collaboration with CleverFoodS project	Before the end of the project	
Budapest	<p>March 23rd, 2023</p> <p>Conference of the Metropolitan Food Roundtable in Budapest.</p> <p><i>Attendees:</i> actors related to urban food systems (district governments, national government agencies, local producers, associations of retailers, caterers and producers, research institutes, etc.).</p> <p><i>Purpose:</i> to find common points of interest, strategies, and areas to work.</p>	Fall 2024	
Lisbon	October 2024	October 2024	Not applicable
Lucca	2025	Before the end of the project	Not applicable

5.1.2 FOODCLIC ADVOCACY OPPORTUNITIES AND RELATED KPIS²¹

FoodCLIC's advocacy pitches and talking points contribute to the overall KPIs of FoodCLIC's D5.2 Communication and Dissemination Strategy, including:

- At least 4 policy briefs including recommendations and guidance related to the type of support that national governments could provide to facilitate the transformation of city-regional food systems across Europe
- Webinars designed around the policy brief topics
- Presentations covering the policy brief topics and targeting policy makers (contributes to the 80+ presentations mentioned in the C&D plan)
- Workshops and network meetings organised within the project including those focused on the formation of a European Food Policy Network platform (D2.1 and D2.2, D4.4 and T4.3).
- Presentations at events in the partner city-regions covering the policy brief topics (contributes to the 80+ presentations mentioned in the C&D plan)
- Video and Vlog creation
- Social media posts
- Newsletter dissemination

²¹ See D5.2 Communication and Dissemination Plan for further details.

- Representation of the policy briefs at the mid-term international workshop and final high-level conference

Additionally, opportunities to synergise with the [Food Policy Coalition](#) and with food-related national campaigns will be explored.

The table ‘advocacy priorities of city-regions’ shows the priority of each of FoodCLIC’s advocacy topics in each of the city-regions.

Table 2: Advocacy Priorities of City-regions.

CITY-REGION	CLIMATE AND NATURE	URBAN / RURAL	HEALTH	FOOD SECURITY / SOVEREIGNTY
Aarhus	1	2	3	4
Amsterdam	4	1	3	2
Barcelona	4	3	2	1
Berlin	3	2	4	1
Brasov	1	4	2	3
Budapest	2	1	2	3
Lisbon	1	4	2	3
Lucca	4	2	3	1

PARTNERS

CONTACT US:

www.foodcllc.eu

#foodcllc

foodcllc.beta@vu.nl

[LinkedIn: @FoodCLIC](#)

Funded
by the European Union